

Vanguard Node Status

Jun 30, 2023

This table outlines the functionality provided by each Vanguard node on the above date. Green indicates the functionality is provided, with links where possible. White means no information / not support, and orange indicates partially supported.

Vanguard Node	Data Discovery	Data Reception	Storage and Interfaces	Access Management Tools	Processing
Belgium	https://beacon-network-demo.ega-archive.org/members	Using Galaxy (http://193.190.80.5:59980/)	Using Galaxy (http://193.190.80.5:59980/)	http://193.191.128.167:3000/	Using Galaxy (http://193.190.80.5:59980/)
Finland	https://beacon-network-demo.ega-archive.org/members	https://gdi-demo.sd.csc.fi/htsget/reads/s3/...		https://gdi-demo.sd.csc.fi/	
Luxembourg	https://beacon-network-demo.ega-archive.org/members	https://htsget.dev.gdi.lu/	https://login.dev.gdi.lu/	https://rems.dev.gdi.lu/	
Netherlands					
Norway	https://ryggve.tsd.usit.uio.no/beacon	https://ryggve.tsd.usit.uio.no/retrieval.html		https://rems.tsd.usit.uio.no	
Spain					
Sweden	https://beacon-network-demo.ega-archive.org/members	https://htsget.gdi.nbis.se/reads/s3/...	https://login.gdi.nbis.se/	https://rems.gdi.nbis.se/	